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Causes and Socio-Ecological Impacts of Rural Resettlement in Ethiopia (Review Article)

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Abstract

Resettlement has been implemented in Ethiopia responding to drought, famine, political and socio-economic issues mismatch of population and environmental conditions, and also to cope with landscapes which could not sufficiently nurture their inhabitants. This review aimed to assess, identify and describe causes and impacts of different rural resettlements socially and ecologically in Ethiopia. Different published and unpublished documents were assessed and described. The review identifies that in Ethiopia, the rural resettlement has long history, as old as more than 800 years whether it was planned or non-planned type and or for political, religious and socio-economical purposes due to different causes. However, well organized and massive rural resettlement in Ethiopia was occurred after mid-20th century as a result of drought, famine, political issues, over population and a food insecurity problem which was hurt the northern and eastern part of the country. Since 1950, about 6 million peoples displaced from their original places and resettled to different forested and sparsely populated areas of the central, southwestern and western part of the country until 2018. The massive resettlements were aimed to ensure the minimum food requirement per man and to provide improved livelihood by enhancing socio-economic and physical infrastructures. However, there are still many gaps and various drawbacks of ecological and environmental degradation, deforestation and human conflicts with each other and with natural resources in general. Therefore, the rural resettlement alone should not be taken as the best alternative to minimize drought and famine or ensure food security while to guarantee effective food security in the long run, other environmental and forest resources conservation strategies should be adopted. Finally, a sustainable forest ecosystem services and land productivity of the resettlement areas have to be ensured through implementation of different integrated and intensified locally attainable and environmental friendly livelihood and agricultural technologies.

Key Words: Ecological and Social Impacts, Environment, Ethiopia, Forest Resources, Rural Resettlement, Sustainability

1. Introduction

Resettlement has been implemented throughout the World, no matter how is their development level and accordingly, resettlement has been employed by many African governments in general and specifically in Ethiopia. Historical, political, cultural, and agro-ecological factors have played an important role in individuals' and families' decisions to locate in certain areas [1]. Resettlement or 'The process by which individuals or a group of people leave spontaneously or unspontaneously their original settlement sites to resettle in new areas where they can begin new trends of life by adapting themselves to the

biophysical, social and administrative systems of the new environment' [2]. In many African governments resettlements aimed to respond to the mismatch of population numbers and environmental conditions, to cope with landscapes which could not sufficiently nurture their inhabitants [3].

According to [4], yet the country is not wealthy enough to respond to or mitigate natural and man-made crises through government aid intervention alone. In Ethiopia, a climatic crisis accentuated a political crisis, and one of the ways in which the government responded to both problems

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was through imposed migration (forced and voluntary) policies which was mostly directed toward more sparsely populated and forest covered lowland areas [2]. Though there are many catalysts promoting population variability due to displacements in any country, Ethiopia appears to be a good example of climatic and political agents interacting to elicit significant changes in population distribution [5].

However, many Authors have been argued on the strategies, policies and consequent impacts of rural resettlement being undertaken in the world, especially in many developing countries due to its impacts on deforestation and climate change [6]-[10]. Moreover, a lot of efforts have gone into developing resettlement typologies to better understand the resettlement process, monitor and assess the impacts of resettlement, and reduce its negative consequences [11]. Therefore, this review is aimed to identify the causes and Socio-ecological impacts occurred related to the rural resettlement in Ethiopia.

2. General Overview of Resettlement

Despite of its different causes and purposes, rural resettlement is worldwide action. Resettlement processes in Ethiopia has been undertaken since early 12th century that results from a combination of religious, physical, political, socio-economic, administrative, technical and managerial phenomena rather than from biological need [9]. Owing to natural calamity, pressure upon resources, political instability, ethnic and land use conflicts, different ethnic groups have moved to and from settlement sites, either of their own free will or because of external interference. In the last 40 years, the political leaderships of Ethiopia have attempted to integrate the process of resettlement into their national development plans and programs. The planned resettlement of 2003 was the most recent example of this trend in Ethiopia and constitutes one of the most massive rural reorganization actions in the Country [7], [10]. However, most of the resettlement schemes have not succeeded in improving the basic necessity of life; rather, they have led to environmental degradation [2]

2.1. History of Rural Resettlement in Ethiopia

The southward non-planned resettlement in Ethiopia was started early in 12th century, which was mainly aimed and depended on the expansion of religious boundaries [2]. During this time, the kings of Aksum extended their rules and controlled land resources over the port of Zeila in the Red Sea, the Saho territory in the south and the Beja plateau in the north (in the region of Eritrea), the Muslim-Arabs were attracted by the resources along the Red Sea coasts. As a result, they converted the local peoples to Islam in the seventh century [2], [8]. Due to population pressure and drought, the Muslim pastoralists from Somalia moved and resettled along the fertile land of Wabe Shebele river in Ethiopia, and they in turn converted many people to Islam. Through the expansion of Islam in Ethiopia, Aksum lost its trade link with the Mediterranean world, which forced its kings to move to Lasta in Wollo in the 12th century and much later to Gondar [2].

As a counteract to Muslim invasion, Amde Syon (1314-1344) invaded a vast territory of the east and south, converted many people to Christianity, and established resettlement sites, such as churches, palaces, and residences. However, the resettlement expansion was interrupted both by internal and external forces. In order to defend Islam, the Ottoman Turks invaded and established resettlement sites along Massawa and Harkiko in the 1500s [2], [6]. When the Abyssinian kingdom was weakened, the Muslims of Adal (Afar), who were helped by Ottoman Turks, established resettlement sites along the Awash-Valley and in some parts of the highland regions of Ethiopia in 1530. In the name of Christianity, the Portuguese established resettlement sites at Massawa in Ethiopia and the island of Socotra in the entrance of the Red Sea in the 16th century. The struggle between the Portuguese and the Ottoman Turks over the land resources, commercial routes to the Arabian Sea and the sea routes to India brought resource degradation and stagnation. The above mentioned factors led to a northward resettlement [12].

Between the 1950s and 1970s, short- and long-distance non-planned resettlement processes took place both within and between regions. It is

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estimated that over one million people were resettled spontaneously in various parts of the country [2]. The major push factors for such non-planned resettlement were: land degradation, poor economic conditions, and land tenure systems, introduction of commercial farms, and unemployment or underemployment [2], [7].

In general, the short- and the long-distance, non-planned resettlement processes played a crucial role in cultural assimilation between the different ethnic groups and adaptation of the physical environment in many parts of the country. However, equal distribution of wealth and political power and technological development were lacking [10], [2]. Due to the low level of development and lack of innovation, rural Ethiopia still depends mainly on outmoded agricultural systems. As a result, ethnic and land-use conflicts, deforestation, depletion of soil nutrients, and shortage of food still persist, creating the need for planned resettlement [2].

On the other hand, between 1957-1974, 1975-1983, and 1984-1991, a set of voluntary and involuntary, long- and short-distance planned resettlements were taking place in various parts of the country. Accordingly, the first resettlement program was established in 1959 at Abela (Sidamo region) and accommodated 700 farmers from the populated upland areas [13]. Due to the development of commercial farms in the Awash-Valley, the Afar pastoralists lost their grazing and water rights.

The 1975-83 planned resettlements following the 1972-73 famine (the worst in Ethiopian contemporary history), the 1974 revolution and the 1975 land reform program, the Mengistu government introduced two types of long-distance planned resettlement: the "low-cost" resettlement and the "special resettlement." The former was established mainly on state farms (formerly commercial farms). Resettlers benefited from the infrastructure and machinery available at the farm site. They were organized into Peasant Associations (PAs) and encouraged to engage in socialist forms of cooperative ventures. They were

allowed to cultivate specified land holdings individually [2].

The planned resettlement between 1974 and 1991, Mengistu's government introduced two types of large-scale resettlement programs: planned resettlement (Sefera) and Villagization (Mender Misreta). Under villagization programs, 35 percent of the total peasants were resettled in nucleated villages by 1988 in altitudinal regions (> 1500 m a.s.l.). Under the planned resettlement, 600,000 peasants were moved from densely populated areas to the scarcely populated lowland regions (< 1500 m a.s.l.) at a distance of about 800 km from their original settlements [2], [9] (Woube 2005 and Shibru 2011). About 12,000 households (60,000 people) from Western Hararghe resettled in the Chewaka since 2003 [8].

2.2. Causes (Factors) of Ethiopian Resettlements

2.2.1. Drought, Famine and War conditions

These phenomena were especially occurred in the southern part of the country [2]. Presently, mass starvation in Sub-Saharan Africa due to natural and man-made disasters is becoming less surprising. But the reality is that poverty and destitution are becoming almost permanent features of most of the rural areas of the sub-continent. While famine episodes induced from drought and ecological degradation are almost eradicated from most of our present day world, the frequency of their occurrence in Africa is increasing from time to time [14]. Far from being the consequence of climatic vagaries, their famines are the symptoms and effects of a crisis in the relationship between human communities and their living environment which is a crisis of livelihood [15].

As a matter of fact, since the infamous famine of 1973-74 the Ethiopian dry lands have been assisted by food-relief programs on a permanent basis. In 1984-85, three million peoples were affected by hunger throughout the country. The number increased to 10 million during the 1998-2001 drought, although causalities greatly decreased due to the improved emergency capacity of national and international agencies [16], and the socio-economic impact of droughts becomes

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progressively more dramatic, affecting a growing portion of rural population.

Indeed, considering population growth merely as an oversized reproduction of present pressure of poverty, it's quite normal to forecast a potential crisis [15], [16], [17]. The forest and the woodland, capital source of food, fuel wood, medicine...etc, are seriously menaced by the rapidly increasing human and animal population. The pressure exerted on environmental resources is causing the decline in food production [17].

2.2.2. Food insecurity

Food insecurity is defined as a complete lack or decline in access to productive resources, in particular land; deterioration of the household asset position overtime and declining resource productivity as a result of environmental degradation [16].

From a descriptive analysis based upon data concerning 38 sub-Saharan African countries observed that traditional production system in Africa seems completely indifferent in front of

rapid population growth [10], [18]. The absence of sufficient technological change in agricultural practice plays in the sense of worsening land degradation process: increased population growth and subsequent heavier density have been accompanied by intensification of land use [19], [16].

Although the most purposes of rural resettlement in Sub Saharan African countries is to provide better livelihood and to ensure food security at the aggregate level, both the number of food-insecure people (those consuming less than 2,100 calories per day) in SSA and the distribution food gap are projected to rise over the next decade [20]. Accordingly (fig. 1), the distribution gap which takes into account unequal purchasing power within countries. Both of these indicators are expected to increase at a slower rate than population growth which brought immigration and causes resources degradation. The region's population growth is among the highest in the world, projected at roughly 2.8 percent per year through 2022 [21].

Sub-Saharan Africa is projected to face an increase in the number of food-insecure people and the food distribution gap over the next decade

Source: USDA, Economic Research Service.

Figure 1. The relationship between number of food insecure people and Food distribution gap.

2.2.3. Agricultural land expansion and rapid population growth

It is believed that population is growing at about 3 percent per year, while no region in the sub-

continent has a record of agricultural output increasing at 3 percent [16], [19]. The urgent need of African population is the constant transfer of technology as well as development of its human

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resources so that people could develop mechanisms by which they can manage to live on their own natural resources and cope up with situation of ecological degradation and drought which are becoming permanent features of the continent rather than acquiring food aid [19].

The major objective of the 1984/85 resettlement programme in Ethiopia which was to reduce the population/resource disequilibrium and to improve the situation of drought-affected people, which was only partly achieved, due to numerous problems associated with this programme as well as exogenous factors [2]. Additionally, the studies on desertification found that the growth of nomadic and subsistence farmer population, combined with increased livestock density, led to increased fuel demand, deforestation and the extension of agricultural and grazing activity into forests and semi-arid marginal lands; all these factors result associated with increased desertification [16], [19].

2.2.4. To introduce physical and social infrastructure, and improved agricultural technologies

The planned resettlement of 1981 – 1999 provided transportation, food, basic needs, agricultural implements, and health care. In 1988, for example, the Mengistu government allocated 822 tractors (with the aim to clear 110,000 hectares of forest and bush land) in the Conventional resettlement; 27,985 farm oxen in the integrated resettlement areas; seeds, and other types of agricultural inputs [12]. In a joint venture, the Settlement Authority and the Relief and Rehabilitation Commission (RRC) resettled 110,090 persons on 88 different resettlement sites between 1975 and 1983. The resettlers were transported to the new residence sites by RRC, which the government mandated to provide resettlers with food, seeds, technical support, credit, buildings, agricultural machinery, and other types of inputs until they become self-supporting [2].

However, these resettlements lack a "development-oriented resettlement" policy in which the Chinese government has carried out TGP displacement and resettlement. The principal goal of this policy requires that involuntarily displaced

persons be assisted in their efforts to improve their former production levels, income earning capacity, and living standards, or at least to restore them to before-project levels or before actual displacement. The Chinese government successfully motivated some 141,000 rural residents to move out of their origin counties in the reservoir area between 2000 and 2004 [22].

2.2.5. Expansion of Socio-cultural boundaries

Prior to the 1950s, two major historical non-planned resettlement situations took place in southern and northern Ethiopia. It can be argued that the major push factor for these resettlement processes was the control of land resources, although religion was ostensibly used to justify war [12]. For the resettlement of people from 12th century to mid-20th century, it can be contended that population pressure upon resources, technological development, and climate can be seen as main factors for the northward and southward resettlement processes, although religion was a motive.

As already mentioned, the Beja and the Saho pastoralists were invaded by the kingdom of Aksum; the Beja in turn pushed the Baria from their alluvial valleys of the Gash and Atbara rivers in southern Eritrea. In the 16th century, the Gurage people moved from the rugged and populated area of Gura in Eritrea to resettle in an area located south of the Awash-river, west of Lake Ziway and east of the Omo River. The Northerners moved to the south and southwest because the latter's fertile highlands were sparsely settled, and agriculture was at a rudimentary stage [2], [10].

2.2.6. Climate change and Environmental Degradation

Climate variability over the last three decades of the 20th century resulted in droughts, famines, and locust outbreaks in several countries of Africa where all of them being catalysts of decisive changes in the political development of such countries and causes of dramatic population displacements [23], [18]. Ethiopia is also seen as one of the African countries most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, with limited capacity to

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cope with short-term climatic shocks or adapt to longer-term trends [24].

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (fig. 2), countries like Ethiopia are likely to suffer extremely from the adverse

effect from climate change because of global warming problem which is caused from the environmental degradation [25], [26]. It is further predicted that Ethiopia is likely to experience a high frequency of extreme climate events, like droughts and floods [25].

Figure 2. Stages of economic development

Source: *Economic growth and the environment* (2003).

2.2.7. Other Factors

Depending on the information from [2], [10], [15], The 1975 land reform programs; The 1977 Ethio-Somali conflict over the Ogaden region; The establishment of RRC and the Settlement Authority; Shortages in arable land in many of the original settlement areas; and The establishment of mass organizations were also the major factors of rural resettlement.

2.3. Types of Resettlement

In Ethiopia, two major types of resettlement processes non-planned and planned have occurred

(fig. 3). According to [2], non-planned resettlement includes spontaneous, emergency, and forced movement of people to a new site.

1. Planned resettlement includes both voluntary and involuntary movement of people to resettle elsewhere. Many interwoven factors influence these processes, some of which are historical, socio-politico economic, physical, technological, and cultural.
2. Non-planned Resettlement: The Pre-1950s Population Movement

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Figure 3. Analytical Model of the Resettlement Process and Other Environmental Factor

Source: (Woube 2005)

3. Impacts of Rural Resettlement

3.1. Socio-economic Impacts

The availability and deterioration of land resources have been the pull and push factors respectively for resettlement in Ethiopia, although these have been obscured by religious war, ethnic conflict, and shortage of food [2], and on the one hand, the resettlement processes have given rise to cultural adaptation, and on the other hand they have led to depletion of resources and land-use conflict. Therefore, experts in development studies continue to forecast that Sub-Saharan Africa is likely to be the only continent to experience a persistent high level of mortality due to food deficiency related problems, as well as an increase in absolute poverty. If death due to absolute hunger or famine is controlled, it will be replaced by death due to malnutrition [19], [21], [27]. Food deficit is still the major killer in this Sub-Saharan continent [16]. In this connection, [27] reported that in the course of the emergency resettlement process about 33 000 settlers lost their lives due to disease, hunger and exhaustion.

Despite the historical reasons why people have settled in one region or another, the Ethiopian government has practiced land redistribution for decades [9], [12], [19]. Redistribution, often referred to as “resettlement”, took place due to overcrowding throughout the Ethiopian highlands. In resettlement programs under the Marxist Derg government, during the 1970s and 1980s, households were moved to seven randomly selected sites. The locations chosen for resettlements were generally not suited for agriculture and in the first year of the program, as many as 5.5% of those resettled died of starvation [27], [28]. In addition, as many of these locations were in the western lowlands, many settlers died of diseases that did not exist in the highlands. Cultural factors and ethnic strife generated problems between the resettled and host populations. Ultimately, as many as 14% of resettled families returned to their original homes and some moved to cities [28].

A voluntary version of the resettlement program was implemented under the present federal democratic government. However, the program was voluntary only in the sense that those being relocated were given a choice about doing so; the

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concerns and issues of the host populations were not addressed [29]. As a result, the “voluntary” resettlement program was still unsuccessful, primarily due to animosity from host populations. Therefore, many resettlers returned to their original homes or migrated to larger cities [28], [1]. On other side, resettlement can create legal pluralism problems of mismatching and conflict between the original population and the new settlers. One study in Kaffa and Kambata of southwestern Ethiopia identified that more than 20 years after resettlement for the new settlers, the resettlement entailed the shift from an intense agro-based livelihood to a forest-based livelihood system, which they had no experience with and were not prepared for [3].

Using the 1998 migration, gender and health survey in five regions of Ethiopia, and multivariate regression techniques, the relationship between internal migration and household living conditions finds a significant living condition advantage of permanent and temporary migrants over non-migrants, primarily linked to migration selectivity by education and non-agricultural income [30], that is why the government policies of resettlement in the 1980s and ethnic federalism of the 1990s may have engendered stress migration and exacerbated poor living outcomes for return migrants.

Research in developing countries confirms that the poor primarily live in rural areas and are predominantly dependent on agriculture [18], [19], [24]. In Ethiopia, rural areas are identified as the worst hit by drought and famine. With no fundamental technological restructuring of agriculture and little or no potential returns to education in the sector, more educated people are likely to continue to migrate to urban areas, thereby depriving rural areas the much needed human capital to boost their transformation and development [30].

3.2. Climate Change

Carbon emissions from tropical land-use change are a major uncertainty in the global carbon cycle. This can be admitted due to agricultural land expansions, consequently cause resettlements. In African woodlands, small-scale farming and the need for fuel are thought to be reducing vegetation

carbon stocks [31]. Removal of forest cover through deforestation is the primary contributor to GHG emissions from changes in forest area. Forest degradation from high impact logging, shifting cultivation, wildfires, and forest fragmentation also contributes to GHG emissions while these actions can lead to rural population displacements [32].

Comenetz and Caviedes argues that from the many countries in Africa affected by ENSO events, Ethiopia is unique in that documented population movements can be explained partially as the result of environmental crises (droughts/famines) caused by climatic variations [33].

In Ethiopia, a climatic crisis accentuated a political crisis, and one of the ways in which the government responded to both problems was through imposed migration policies. Because migration (forced and voluntary) was mostly directed toward more sparsely populated areas and led to changes in the ethnic balance and the demographic effect of El Nino can be observed in Ethiopian demographic records [2], [12], [34]. Though there are many catalysts promoting population variability due to displacements in any country, Ethiopia appears to be a good example of climatic and political agents interacting to elicit significant changes in population distribution [33].

3.3. Ecological Degradation

This term is used to describe the process of deterioration and reduction in the quality of life of humans and the living environment. Ecological degradation is a process that unfolds gradually and is apparently manifested by serious land degradation and deforestation. Usually, degradation of the ecology is seen under land degradation, water resource degradation, loss of biodiversity, deforestation and an expanding process of desertification [34], [16].

Many studies indicated the negative impacts of resettlement on different ecosystems. For instance, according to [35] the highest deforestation period in some parts of Ethiopia (specifically, in Yeki) overlapped with large-scale resettlement that increased demographic pressure, investment, and competition for land and forest resources. Tadesse

also argued that even though the resettlement program of the 1984-85 was intended to promote food security and to reduce population pressure of vulnerable areas, it brought increased pressure on the settled landscapes that resulted in undesirable consequences of ecological degradation.

3.4. Environmental Impacts

It is important to define the terms: environment, settlement, resettlement and resettlement schemes. In [2] (Woube 2005), environment is defined as the surrounding community and has a multidisciplinary implication, which has both physical and social characteristics while Settlement exists within the physical environment (fig. 4). In the southwestern forested areas, resettlers have been modifying the natural landscape and ecosystem functions to intensify certain provisioning services, such as food supply at the expense of others, for example, regulating services regardless of their sustainability [19]. Baird and Shoemaker discussed that resettlement schemes which have been carried out in Laos, with regard to the physical environment the program lack environmental impact assessment and environmental management plan which causes aggravated transformation of LULC in the study areas [11].

Some of the bio-physical factors look inevitable in the analysis of environmental suitability for human resettlement so that environment is one of the issues composed of the

interaction of complicated variables [36]. It is difficult to consider only one variable separately for the analysis of its suitability for human resettlement. This is particularly because they are naturally interwoven in a complicated system. Paradoxically, it is equally difficult to evaluate all environmental factors at a time in case of this, environmental suitability of Chawaka resettlement site has been analyzed in terms of bio-physical and socio-economic environmental factors [15]. In the last century, despite (or perhaps because of) the availability of modern technologies, the modernizing efforts by several governments, the liberalization of much of the Ethiopian economy and its integration to the international market, the country’s capacity to cope with environmental extremes has been steadily decreasing [16], especially from the 1960s onwards this has taken the shape of a permanent “livelihood and environmental crisis”.

These environmental impacts of rural resettlements are being serious problems in the many countries of the World. In China, although the construction of the Three Gorges dam which can protect the vast areas and millions of inhabitants downstream the dam from the threat of floods, and generate electricity to meet the need of industrial growth and domestic consumption, there are some environmental effects produced by human resettlement, urban relocation and reconstruction, and relocation of industrial enterprises have turned out to be crucial [22]

Figure 4. *Environment, Settlement, and Resettlement Processes (Woube 2005).*

In general, local people attitude and practice on their environment is indeed decisive to sustainability of resources [19]. For many years people took for granted the environment in which they lived or depended. They thought that the environment is in-exhaustible can go for ever as it is. That such attitude is short-sighted became widely apparent when the extent of land degradation and desertification related human suffering was exhibited by the widespread droughts that tragically affected the Sub-Saharan Africa between the late 1960s and now [17], [36]. Since then both public

3.5. Natural Resources Degradation Impacts

3.5.1. Deforestation and Forest Degradation

At the beginning of this century, the southwestern part of the Ethiopian Highlands had still been completely covered by montane rainforests [37], [38]. Shifting cultivation, which had been practiced since centuries within the area had not been really a threat for the forest resources. However, the situation changed with new settlers migrating from the central and northern parts of the country to SW Ethiopia. With the new settlers, a new farming system was introduced in to the forest areas that was not adapted to the environmental conditions in the area [4], [39].

The forest degradation in Ethiopia is closely linked to the ongoing population growth. More people generally lead to an increasing demand on land for living and for agricultural production. The situation got more severe in the eightieth when large numbers of people moved to SW Ethiopia in scope of organized resettlement programs [26]. Consequently the pressure on the forest resources themselves increased due to a higher demand on fuelwood and construction timber. Finally, uncontrolled logging and the illegal export of wood stems to urban centers like Addis Ababa is a threat for the natural high forest of the country. The natural regeneration of the forest resources is difficult due to high populations of grazing and browsing livestock within the forests [39].

According to the study which was undertaken by [35], in Yeki and Decha of southwestern Ethiopia to understand the extent of

and decision makers have become increasingly concerned with changes in environmental quality resulting from human activities.

This phenomenon continued, and in the wake of the 1985 famine, the Ethiopian government launched an ambitious program of environmental reclamation supported by donors and nongovernment organizations and backed by the largest food-for-work program in Africa without research on their environmental impact or their economic costs and benefits [28], [32].

forest cover changes through time, and to explore how deforestation rates correlate with (a) local changes in settlement, demographic conditions, and livelihood practices, and (b) broader changes in land-tenure and agricultural development policies in Ethiopia, over 36% of the forests were lost since 1973 and deforestation rates varied through time due to changes in land-tenure and agricultural development policies. According to [23], annual deforestation rate was recorded as 3.02% in 5 decades in the south western Ethiopia from 1957-2007. The interactions in agricultural policy, land-tenure, demographic dynamics, and conservation policies with forest stability or decline shows the importance of carefully considering the undesirable effects of resettlement and agricultural development policies and the need to support community forest conservation that also benefits local people.

Among the main drivers of forest cover change in the globe, resettlement entails the prime position, especially in the tropical developing countries. Alemu indicated that the resettlement programmes in Ethiopia, specifically in Amhara and Southern regions had some positive effects on some livelihood outcome variables such as more income, food security and reduced poverty [12], [17]. However, these livelihood outcome changes were not sustainable because of poor adaptation, environmental destruction and unwise use of natural resources following the resettlement, and he suggested that livelihood can be sustainable only if there is a strategy to cope with vulnerabilities/shocks and to strengthen capabilities and assets both at present and in the long run [10].

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Since the 1970s, peasants were resettled in large scale state-enforced programs from the drought-prone and degraded central Ethiopia to the forested areas of the south-west. The basic rationale behind was to facilitate resource rehabilitation in central Ethiopia and to provide poor peasants with a better livelihood [4].

Most of the resettlement programs recently have been undertaken in western and south western Oromia, Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples Regional State (SNNPRS) as well as in the western lowlands of Tigray and Amhara regional states, where the first two states' were harsher due to deforestation and forest degradation caused by overestimated numbers of resettlers [9].

3.5.2. Loss of Biodiversity

The most problem of different rural resettlements in southwestern parts of Ethiopia is its *Table 1. Summary of Rural Resettlements in Ethiopia*

consequence of Land-use land cover change, which is a major driver of biodiversity loss and ecosystem service degradation, is caused by intertwined local and regional forces that shape human-environment interactions [19], [35].

Relocating peoples will shorten fallow periods which would have resulted in soil and forest degradation, and subsequent large declines in crop production. In turn, this has led to the degradation of wildlife and forest resources, as people have attempted to substitute losses in food production with other sources of income and food [11], [36]. From an environmental perspective, the transition from Sweden to other land uses often contributes to permanent deforestation, loss of biodiversity, increased weed pressure, declines in soil fertility, and accelerated soil erosion [6].

S. No	Reset. Year	Reset. Type	No of People	Main Causes	Main Effects	Major Place of Resettlement	
						From	To
1	Before 1950	Non-planned	unknown	Religious	Ethnic & religious conflict	Between	and within regions
2	1950-1970	Non-planned	>1,000,000	land degradation, poor economic conditions, land tenure systems, introduction of commercial farms, and unemployment or underemployment	ethnic conflict and degradation of human and land resources	Between	and within regions
3	1971-1983	Planned	>110,000	Famine, Revolution and Land reform program	degradation of human and land resources	Northern and Eastern parts of the country	Central, South, Southwestern and western parts
4	1984-1991	Planned	>600,000	Over population, agricultural land expansion and famine	Deforestation, Land degradation	Northern and Eastern High land areas	West and Southwestern lowlands
5	1991-2003	Planned	>600,000	Over population, agricultural land expansion, social and physical infrastructure	Ethnic conflicts, Deforestation, Forest and Land degradation	Northern, Eastern and Southeastern	Western and Southwestern
6	2003-2018	Non-planned	>3,500,00	Ethnic conflicts, Drought, Political instability, flooding	Hunger, shortage of shelter, others	Eastern, western, and from most borders	Central and near to centers
Total			>6,000,000				

From the above table we can understand that rural resettlement has long age in Ethiopia with different causes and effects. Additionally, the resettlement processes has displaced more than 6 million peoples from their original places.

4. Drawback or Limitations of Rural Resettlement in Ethiopia

There are some contradicting ideas among the studies already undertaken on the rural resettlements of Ethiopia. According to [33], in contrast to other African countries affected by climatic crises related to El Nino, Ethiopia has established a regular demographic enumeration schedule, and conducted censuses before and after the 1982–83 and 1991–93 El Nino events while still the country is not wealthy enough to respond to or mitigate such crises through government aid intervention alone.

However, most studies are indicating that there are no official or accessible pre-settlement statistics on how many people in total have been and or to be resettled or dislocated in Ethiopia over the past decades [8], [9], [26], [36]. As a result, the number of rural resettlers assigned to be resettled in Chewaka (Southwestern Ethiopia) in 2003 was over estimated and some of them were obligated to be resettled in the dense natural forest areas.

The other lack is that the resettlement programme did not support the resettlers to diversify their livelihood strategies and most of the resettles dominantly exercised traditional agriculture. Resettlers' involvement in non-farm and off-farm activities is insignificant. It is clear that agriculture is highly vulnerable to environmental changes [10], [36].

Additionally, the resettlement scenario and its consequence on forest resources during the Derge regime can be categorized as frontier economy paradigm type. As depicted in the above explanations, the concern was on achieving food security at the expense of forest resource. It was totally anthropocentric in its nature [9].

5. Summary and Conclusions

Generally, resettlement has been employed by Ethiopian governments as far as many African governments did it to respond to the drought, famine, political issues, socio-economic issues, mismatch of population numbers and environmental conditions, to cope with landscapes which is

difficult or could not sufficiently nurture their inhabitants. However, the well organized and massive rural resettlement in Ethiopia was occurred after mid-20th century as a result of drought, famine, political issues, over population and food insecurity problems which were hurt the southern and eastern part of the country. The massive displacement was undertaken voluntarily and involuntarily to the forested and sparse populated areas of the central, southwestern and western part of the country until 2003. Although the main purposes of the massive resettlements were to ensure the minimum food requirement per man and to provide improved livelihood by enhancing socio-economic and physical infrastructure, there is still a wide gap between food insecurity and total population growth.

Additionally, various drawbacks of ecological and environmental degradation, deforestation and human conflicts with each other and natural resources in general were identified from this review. Accordingly, if these issues are ignored in the over increasing population size which leads the agricultural land expansions in to the natural forest resources, we have no evidence that the drought and famine that they escaped from their original residences will not come in the current resettlement areas.

6. Recommendations

- i. The current studies identify and discuss the declining of forest and other natural resources of various Ethiopian rural resettlement areas with many gaps which need further studies for sustainable development in the rural resettlement areas.
- ii. The issues of biodiversity conservations, climate change, lack of diversified agricultural practices and the sustainability in the communities' livelihood adoptions are the main limitations need further integrated agricultural activities in most parts of the resettlement areas. Especially, the correlation of forestry, Climate change and local livelihood is not practically considered rather than being documented.
- iii. Therefore, the rural resettlement alone should not be taken as the best alternative to minimize drought and famine or ensure food security

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- while to guarantee effective food security in the long run, other strategies should be adopted.
- iv. Livelihood diversification and agricultural intensification (expansion of non-farm economic activities like ecotourism, agro-forestry, and apiculture, mid and lowland fruit productions, livestock fattening through cut and carry method) which can minimize the pressure on the remaining forest resources of the country is need to be pushed.
 - v. Reversing the paradox- rehabilitation of the degraded area (resource management and eco-development paradigm) versus degrading the remaining forest resource (frontiers and environment protection paradigm) has to be checked. Rather than converting forest and wood lands into agricultural land (be it investment or small holder agriculture), it is better to enhance the productivity of the existing cultivated land in one hand and develop eco-friendly economic activity on the remaining forest resources (like apiculture, ecotourism, fruit and spices production)
 - vi. When resettlement is the only option to be applied, special attention should be given to minimize its adverse effect. In addition, priority should be given to eco-friendly economic activities rather than agriculture or intensification has to be used in order to minimize additional demand of cultivable land at the expense of forests and woodlands.
 - vii. Moreover, future research should also collect qualitative data in addition to the quantitative one to provide further insight on the implementation of the intervention and draw context-specific lessons to improve management in similar programs.

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